

A study on the relationship of thinking style and academic adjustment of higher secondary students

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ABSTRACT

Background: Adjustment is the psychological process of adapting to, coping with, and managing the problems of everyday life. Adjustment to the educational environment is a major element to predict educational achievements. Analysing students' thinking can help them plan their learning strategies. It aids them to be extra systematized in their schoolwork. The present study intends to find out the relationship between thinking style and academic adjustment of higher secondary students.

Methodology: Simple random technique was used in the study and the sample consists of 100 students from Chennai district. The investigation of data was achieved with regression analysis.

Findings: The study found there is a significant relationship between Thinking Style and Academic Adjustment among Higher Secondary Students.

Keywords: Academic Adjustment, Thinking Style, Higher Secondary Students

Introduction

Education makes a man wise and self-dependent. It is the only sustainable wealth. When they get a good education, their living standard, satisfaction and dignity will also increase. Today people consider education as the foundation of their children's future dream castle without discrimination.

In today's education system, students study under pressure from parents, peers, and teachers. The elementary characteristic of human being is the capacity of thinking. A student's knowledge is sharpened by asking multiple questions from one answer. Thoughtfulness is the main distinguishing feature of human life. All students have unique preferred ways of thinking and learning that psychologists refer to as styles. All styles are adaptive under the right circumstances. In a classroom there will be many students who express different types of

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thinking; teachers should be able to handle the students according to their thinking. Sternberg (1998) defined thinking style as the way an individual thinks. He believed that thinking style is not a capability but refers to the method an individual uses in his capabilities. Education is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits which make a person a good citizen. Scholastic modification means how an individual is conveying his duties towards his learning and whether he can achieve his goal or not. The present study measures the thinking style and academic adjustment of higher secondary students.

Objective of the study

The focus of this study is to examine thinking style and academic adjustment among higher secondary students.

- To predict whether there is any significant relationship between think style and academic adjustment among higher secondary students.

Hypothesis

Based on the objective, the hypothesis was formulated for the study.

- A significant linear relationship between thinking style occurs with academic adjustment.

Variables

The present investigation is an attempt to study the thinking style and academic adjustment of higher secondary students. The variables involved are:

- Thinking Style
- Academic Adjustment scale

Methodology

The participants of this study consisted of 100 higher secondary school students from the population of Chennai district who were selected by simple random sampling. The investigator used a survey method in this research.

Tools used

The *thinking style* was modified and reconstructed by the investigator was used to assess the thinking style of higher secondary consists of 63 items. The reliability of this scale 0.8 was found by Cronbach's Alpha Method. The obtained reliability coefficient is revealing that the tool is reliable.

The *achievement adjustment scale* was constructed by the investigator, consists of 37 items. The reliability of this scale 0.8 was established by Cronbach's Alpha Method. The obtained reliability coefficient is revealing that the tool is reliable.

Statistical techniques used:

Data analysis was performed using multiple linear regression analysis.

The tool used for data collection was a questionnaire. second The questionnaire contains questions on thinking style and academic adjustment. The analysis of data was done using regression. The scale is a liker type scale, with multiple choice responses. Responses range from Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly Disagree. In this five-point scale, the responses are given weight from 1 to 5 given, shown: 5- Strongly Agree, 4- Agree, 3- Undecided, 2- Disagree, and 1-Strongly Disagree.

Analysis of Data and Testing of Hypothesis

In testing the hypothesis stated, the researcher used multiple linear regression analysis.

- **Hypothesis 1:** A significant linear relationship between thinking style exists with achievement adjustment.

Regression analysis was carried out using the independent variable of thinking style and the dependent variable of academic adjustment. The result of the regression analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Multiple Regression of Thinking Style with Academic Adjustment

Code	Independent Variable	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	102.679	20.683		4.964	0.000
X ₁	Thinking Style	1.009	0.149	0.597	6.789	0.000

Multiple R = 0.590, R² = 0.348, F= 25.836

Table 1 shows the coefficient of the relationship between thinking style and the academic adjustment of higher secondary students of the Chennai district. Table 1 show that the relationship coefficient between thinking style and the academic adjustment is 0.36. Hence, the independent variable of thinking style significantly contributed to the academic adjustment. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Results shown in Table 1 were used to perform regression analysis, and the equation is given below. Where Y = Academic Adjustment

$$Y = 1.009 X_1 + 102.679$$

Findings of the study

There was a significant positive relationship between Thinking Style and the Academic Adjustment of Higher Secondary Students of Chennai district.

Conclusion

In this study, the relationship between thinking style and academic adjustment of higher secondary students was investigated. The results of regression analysis indicated that thinking style was significantly predicated by academic adjustment. This shows that students with positive thinking style is tend to have better academic adjustment, than with the students having negative thinking style. The importance of the finding about the relationship between thinking style and academic adjustment depends on the significant implication for education at the level of instruction and assessment as well as at the level of curriculum development and extra-

curricular activities. Because thinking style contributes to academic adjustment, teaching that concentrate on thinking style, in consideration can lead to the development of academic adjustment among students.

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